

ARRANGEMENT OF ARCHITECTURAL ELEMENTS FOR USE IN APPAREL DESIGN.

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Annotation. The article provides a systematization table for the classification of Uzbek national architectural elements and their use in clothing design.

Key words: fashion industry, fashion, design, composition, decoration.

The fashion industry plays a central role in the production of industrial products in the economy of Uzbekistan, because this industry affects the satisfaction of a large part of market needs during the production of consumer goods.

The rapid development of the fashion industry, changing trends and the opportunity to sell products allow many architects to work in the fashion industry. The development of technologies, the search for new means of expression, materials, visual effects - all this is breaking the boundaries between fashion and architecture.

As Coco Chanel said, "Fashion is architecture: the only difference is proportion. Architecture is hardened fashion."

Fashion and architecture come from the same point. Clothing and buildings serve as a means of protection, expression and preservation of the human body. Architects and designers create a shell for a person with two differences: the first in statics, the second in dynamics. A design tool for designers is the human body.

Clothing is the first layer that surrounds a person, and the interior is the second layer. Buildings and everything that fills the city square is the third, largest layer. Architecture and fashion interact with people more often than other forms of art and

can influence their psychological state. The main task of the designer and architect is to provide comfort.

The originality and diversity of clothes is mainly determined by the presence of elements that complement and decorate the costume. The national costumes of each nation have their own decorative structure. For example, Uzbek national clothes are dominated by the use of patterns and ornaments. Patterns are divided into different parts based on their characteristics, and separate painting styles have been developed for clothing, jewelry, wood carving, and many other fields. Among them, the common pattern type for all directions is "Islimi".

Islimi is a type of pattern that connects different ornaments in the composition. It is also known as mainly plant-like pattern. "It is based on the image of an endless spiraling branch, unbounded by dissimilar leaves and flowers, signifying a continuous path to the divine garden. It is one of the most common decorative elements of representatives of the Muslim religion" [1].

There are several types of islimi:

1. "Ordinary islimi" is almond-shaped and located at the tips of spiral branches. This type of "islimi" is often used in embroidery used on clothing.

2. "Winged islimi" differs from "Ordinary islimi" by the complexity of the decoration. A complex element of decoration is divided into two parts similar to a leaf - wings. In relation to the movement of the spiral, the wings open up and down. As a rule, the lower wing is shorter than the upper wing. The tip of the wing can be pointed or rounded. "Winged islimi" is similar to the "bush" pattern [1].

3. The most common type of ornament in Azerbaijan is "Khachali (fork) islimi". In shape, it resembles a broken branch of a tree. It should be noted that the decoration of "Khachali islimi" is partially similar to "Winged islimi".

"Khachali islimi" is more common in Azerbaijani decorations than other Islamic types. "Winged style" and "Khachali style", which have very different forms, took root in all areas of decorative art, even in the patterns of fabrics with complex technological features in the Middle Ages[1].

4. "Butali (almond-shaped) islimi" has an almond-shaped head and was widely used as a decorative element in the Middle East and Azerbaijan.

5. Woven islimi" has a more complex structure than the above. Framed by two wide rims, the "Woven Style" is distinguished by two wings at the front and back. Local craftsmen added new details and elements to the pattern, enriching its artistic appearance. All forms and elements are closely related to each other, and on this basis, the decoration received the name "Woven". This type of pattern has a high artistic complexity and is widely known among modern masters. Artists, modelers use the pattern of "Woven Islimi" when creating decorative and practical art products, along with clothing models, to give these works a national spirit [2].

It should be noted that the early medieval decorations gradually became more complex in the form of patterns and complemented each other. The elegant elements of Islami eventually rose to a high artistic level.

A type of "bush" pattern is a pattern with a curved tip and an almond-shaped top. The motif of the bush is among many peoples of the East. Also known in Middle Eastern countries and Europe.

Craftsmen have widely used this type of pattern in paintings of carpets and fabrics, decoration of clothes, as well as artistic products of decorative and practical art.

The type of pattern called "Cloud" is one of the main elements of pattern art.

It should be noted that the early medieval decorations gradually became more complex in the form of patterns and complemented each other. The elegant elements of Islimi were eventually elevated to a high artistic level. The image below shows an example of an Islimi pattern depicted through wood carving (Fig. 1).

Figure 1.

Also, another type of pattern widely spread in Central Asia, girix - means tangled, knot. A geometric pattern is one of the more complex patterns and consists of rectangles, triangles, circles, and polygons. The structure is divided into gyrix, consisting of straight lines, curved lines and mixed lines. A geometric pattern is made up of continuous reports, and each report has its own structure. In Europe it is called arabesque. The floral wreath consists of plant and geometric pattern elements. Its elements include geometric and plant-like patterns (Fig. 2).

Figure 2.

Table of systematization of architectural ornaments.

Table 1.

№	Color image of architectural ornament	Sketch variant of architectural ornament
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